

Prediction of Fiberglass Rupture by Detected Acoustic Emission

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Acoustic emission of fiberglass composite material during tensile loading is characterized experimentally by a set of records. Regularity of recorded data enables prediction of the sample rupture when approaching the critical loadings. For this purpose a new statistical method is formulated. The prediction is performed by comparing acoustic activity of tested and representative samples. Results of the prediction agree with the experimental data and confirm the hypothesis that acoustic emission detection provides a proper basis for a simple nondestructive testing of very complex fiberglass composite.

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1. Introduction

Acoustic emission (AE) analysis has so far been successfully utilized in detecting the development of defects in materials [1-4] and characterizing cracking of loaded technical structures [5-7]. Therefore, the question arises if it could also be applied to predict the rupture of a material sample or structure already at weak loading when the material is still rather unharmed. Success in this area could contribute to the development of new methods of nondestructive testing intended to prevent the collapse of structural elements in various fields of engineering [1,3]. The purpose of this article is to show how the rupture of fiberglass composite material can be predicted by detection of acoustic emission signal well before the critical loading [5,6].

Acoustic emission occurs practically in all stressed solids, but it is most expressive in composite materials due to their distinctly inhomogeneous structure [3-6,8-11]. Fiberglass is often applied composite material [3,9], and therefore, AE of its sample during a tensile test is treated here. For this purpose the basic

properties of the corresponding experiment are described first.

2. AE of stressed fiberglass samples

Acoustic emission can occur in stressed fiberglass material due to various types of developing defects. The most prominent of them are delamination and rupture of glass fibers [3,6,10-12]. Acoustic signal during fiber rupture is generally more intensive than during its delamination and therefore only this type of emission is further considered. It appears as a series of mutually separated sonic bursts, and therefore, the complete phenomenon is called discrete acoustic emission. Its properties are experimentally characterized by the number of sonic bursts detected by an AE sensor on the sample during properly selected step of load increasing [5,6]. Our main goal is to indicate how the structure of the composite sample is degrading during tensile loading until rupture and how this degradation can be characterized and predicted by the number of detected AE bursts. With this aim we first describe the properties of AE detection system.

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In the experiments we utilized the AE sensor made of a piezoelectric ceramic plate PZT-5A having the resonant frequency of 200 kHz. It was surrounded by a damping material and backing stick in the aluminum housing [5,6]. During measurements the background noise from the surrounding was partially avoided by a selective amplification of transducer signal in the frequency band from 100 kHz to 1 MHz. The noise of the detection system was approximately $10 \mu\text{V}$ with respect to the input.

The amplification factor of the detection system was: 50 000 so that the applicable span of the output was from 0.5 V to 10 V. Before a tensile experiment the sensitivity of AE detection system was characterized by dropping a steel ball of diameter 1 mm from the height of 10 cm to the horizontally placed fiberglass sample. This collision excited in the AE detection system a signal burst with the amplitude in the middle of the detection system span. Similar AE bursts were observed also during elongation of fiberglass samples, and therefore the number N of AE bursts was utilized as the basic variable for the characterization of the observed AE phenomenon.

In the experiments we measured the number dN of observed AE bursts during a small step dL of sample elongation and described the corresponding acoustic activity by the variable: $A = dN/dL$. The basic AE properties during tensile testing were then characterized by recording the acoustic activity A of fiberglass samples in dependence of their relative elongation: $r = dL/L$. In addition, the tensile force F was measured and recorded, while the number of unbroken fibers N was estimated by the difference of the initial number of fibers and the integral of activity A . Since the variables A , F , and N are proportional to the arbitrary selected cross section of the sample, it is reasonable to normalize them to the unit of the vertical scale in the diagram used to characterize the AE properties [6]. Figure 1 shows records of the tensile force $F(r)$ and acoustic activity $A(r)$ in dependence of the relative elongation r . By the properties of these graphs we next describe the

FIG. 1. (Color online) Characteristics of a representative fiberglass material sample during a tensile test. Acoustic activity: A (bottom), tensile force: F (middle), linear graph: F_{lin} (middle-dotted), number of fibers: N (top). Since the magnitudes of A , F , and N are proportional to the arbitrary selected cross section of the sample their graphs are normalized to the unit of the vertical scale.

basic characteristics of AE phenomenon during tensile test of fiberglass samples.

The variables shown in Figure 1 demonstrate AE characteristics during tensile loading of fiberglass material that was used in the industrial production of skis. The sample had a length of $L = 20$ cm, a width of 2 cm and a thickness of 0.2 cm. At the ends, it was glued to metal clamps adapted for testing on a tensile machine [5,6]. The relative sample elongation r and the tensile force $F(r)$ were measured on the machine of tensile testing. The elongation rate was 0.3% per minute. Acoustic activity $A(r)$ of the sample was detected by the resonance AE sensor coupled to the clamp by a drop of oil.

The dashed line (- - -) in Figure 1 shows the linear change of tensile force F_{lin} during the increase of elongation r in the interval from 0 to 5%. This line describes the dependence of the tensile force $F(r)$ approximately in the elongation interval from $r = 0\%$ to $r = 2.5\%$. As the elongation surpasses this interval an increasingly strong non-linear deviation of $F(r)$ from the straight line (- - -) begins to take place,

FIG. 2. (Color online) Records of the normalized tensile force $F(r)$ during elongation of 20 representative samples of fiberglass composite material.

FIG. 3. (Color online) Records of the normalized acoustic activity $A(r)$ during elongation of 20 representative samples of fiberglass composite material.

which at the approach to the critical elongation $r_o = 4.5\%$, turns into a rapid fall and final rupture of the sample. With the transition to the characteristic nonlinear region above $r_n = 2.5\%$, the acoustic emission begins to appear. Its activity $A(r)$ first increases similarly to the third power of the elongation, and later quickly vanishes at the transition to the critical elongation r_o . Since the acoustic activity $A(r)$ represents the number of broken fibers per unit of sample elongation, the total number of broken fibers can be estimated by its integral. This further determines the decreasing of the existing number of fibers $N(r)$ with increasing elongation r . The diagram $N(r)$ is shown together with the diagrams of $F(r)$ and $A(r)$ in Figure 1. Based on the properties exhibited by the records of tensile force $F(r)$ and acoustic activity $A(r)$, we could conclude that they parametrically represent a deterministic relation: $F = F(A)$ by which we could predict specimen rupture due to increasing elongation. For an analytical definition of this relation, we need to know the mechanism of defect development and the accompanying AE due to

relaxation of internal stresses during fiberglass stretching. However, due to the very complex and random structure of the composite material, it is practically impossible to define the function $F(A)$ analytically. To predict the rupture, we therefore use an empirical approach based on a representative set of 20 AE records shown in Figures 2, 3 and 4.

Similar properties of AE characteristics as demonstrated in Figure 1 are also exhibited by the graphs in Figures 2, 3 and 4. However, their parameters, that are quantitatively representing these properties, randomly depend on the properties of samples, and therefore, it is necessary to use statistical methods in their characterization. Figure 2 shows qualitatively similar properties of the stretching force $F(r)$ diagrams as Figure 1, but the parameters that describe the coefficient of elasticity: $k = F(r)/r$, the elongation r_n at the transition to nonlinear region, the maximum value F_m , and the elongation at the sample rupture r_o , are different. Similar properties of the variables $A(r)$ and $N(r)$ are also shown in Figures 3 and 4. Based upon

FIG. 4. (Color online) Records of the normalized number of fibers $N(r)$ during elongation of 20 representative samples of fiberglass composite material.

the representative sets of displayed graphs it is possible to define the values of their characteristic parameters statistically [11].

3. Prediction of fiberglass rupture

Considering the random properties of the tensile force and acoustic activity of the elongated fiberglass samples shown in Figures 2, 3 and 4, we can conclude that it is impossible to predict deterministically when a new sample will break during testing. However, there is a statistical approach to the solution of this problem, which is similar to the prediction of chaotic processes by intelligent systems based on learning [13]. To explain this approach, let us consider how an expert predicts when a new sample will break during tensile test. For this purpose, the expert first performs tests on a set of representative samples and remembers how they behave during the test. He then begins the testing of a new sample and compares its properties with those of the representative samples. At this comparison, he looks for a representative sample whose

properties are most similar to the properties of the sample at the beginning of its test. Based on the behavior of the most similar representative sample during the test, he then predicts how the new sample will break. In order to assess the similarity, he usually applies the minimum difference of the distribution of the measured variables or parameters determined by them.

By comparing the similarity of the distributions of the variables at the beginning of testing, we can draw conclusions about the distribution in the later course of the testing. Such reasoning corresponds to the forecasting of the sample failure from the course of acoustic activity in the initial interval of loading $(0, r_z)$. For this purpose we characterize in the initial loading interval the difference of acoustic activity between the new- (n) and the representative- (s) sample by the norm:

$$D_s = \|A_n(r) - A_s(r)\| \quad (3.1)$$

By the standard deviation σ of the norm (1) and the Gaussian function we next describe the measure of similarity between both samples as:

$$S_s = \exp(-D_s^2/2\sigma^2) \quad (3.2)$$

Based on this measure of similarity, we can formulate the prediction of the force course of the new sample by statistically defined conditional average over all representative force records [13]:

$$F_{pr} = \Sigma_s \{S_s * F_s(r)\} / \Sigma_s S_s \quad (3.3)$$

At its calculation the condition is described by the acoustic activity $A_n(r)$ of the new sample. The smaller the measure of difference D_s , the greater is the measure of similarity between the new and the representative sample S_s and the greater is the contribution of the representative sample to the predicted value of force $F_{pr}(r)$. When an optimal sample with the index o from the representative set is very similar to the new sample, and the others are quite different from it,

FIG. 5. (Color online) Record of the given AE activity A (bottom) in the interval of elongation $(0, 3.25)$ and the predicted force $F_{pr}(r)$ (top -.-) in the interval extending to the rupture of the sample: (r_z, r_o) .

the corresponding values of the similarity measure are: $S_o \approx 1$ and $S_{s \neq o} \approx 0$. Consequently, the course of the predicted force $F_{pr}(r)$ matches quite well with the course of force appertaining to the most similar sample: $F_{pr}(r) \approx F_o(r)$. In such a case, it is not necessary to calculate the statistical average $F_{pr}(r)$ for the rupture prediction because it is enough to find the sample whose acoustic activity optimally matches the activity of the tested one. By using its course of force $F_o(r)$ we can then predict the rupture of tested sample. In the following, such a method is used to predict the course of the force of the sample with the characteristics shown in Figure 1 based on the set of images shown in Figures 2 and 3. In this case, the course of activity $A(r)$ was used in the interval from 0 to $r_z = 3.25$, which is shown in Figure 5.

Above the graph of activity A in Figure 5 there is shown the course of the force predicted on the basis of the representative sample whose acoustic activity A most closely matches the activity of the given sample. The prediction is carried out in the interval extending to the final rupture of the sample: (r_z, r_o) . For the assessment

FIG. 6. (Color online) Records of true F (bottom) and predicted force F_o (top).

FIG. 7. (Color online) Records of the force predicted by the most similar record F_o (bottom) and by the statistically defined conditional average F_{ca} (middle -.-). The top record shows the difference $F_o - F_{ca} + 1$.

of the prediction quality Figure 6 shows records of the true tensile force F and F_o estimated from the most similar sample. In order to compare the forecasting by the most similar pattern with the forecasting by the statistical average, Figure 7 shows the corresponding force records together with their difference.

Records shown on Figures 6 and 7 indicate

that in the case under consideration the most similar record predicts the properties of the given sample better than the statistical average. This property is a consequence of the disruptive force variation over the samples utilized in the statistical average and need not be of general character.

4. Conclusions

Although the structure of the fiberglass composite material is rather complex, our research shows that it is possible to obtain experimentally a proper information for the forecasting of its rupture during tensile loading. For this purpose no detailed classification of defects evolving in the material is needed [11, 12] but just the AE activity of its sample has to be compared with the activity of a representative

set of samples during the same loading test. The representative sample with the most similar course of acoustic activity during loading is then applicable for a simple prediction of the tested sample rupture. A little more extensive is the forecasting based on the statistically determined conditional average since its estimation includes accounting of all representative samples; but the results of both prediction methods do not differ significantly.

At the application of acoustic emission analysis there often appears the question: »How the detected AE signal could be utilized for a quantitative description of the corresponding microscopic phenomenon?« A proper answer usually cannot be provided since the corresponding micro-dynamic phenomenon is far too complex for an analytical treatment [5, 6].

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